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Article · February 2023

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Heian Period: Last Division of Classical Japanese History

1.Introduction

The Heian period is about 400 years from the time the capital of Japan was moved to Kyoto until the establishment of the samurai government in Kamakura. In Nara's Heijo-kyo capital, there was a power struggle between aristocrats and monks. Emperor Kanmu decided to move the capital in an attempt to recognize the government. He moved the capital to Nagaoka-kyo in 784 and then, in 794 he built Heian-kyo in present day Kyoto. The capital of Japan was Kyoto until 1868 when it was moved to present day Tokyo.

In the capital, the aristocratic Fujiwara clan came to power around the 9th century. The Fujiwara clan took the control of the Imperial Court by making their daughters the emperor's wives and placing their children in the position of an emperor from an early age. In those days, it was a matriarchal society and when a boy was born to be emperor's successor, he was raised in his mother family. Therefore, the grandfather of the Fujiwara clan was very powerful and had a great influence on the emperor.

When the emperor was young, the Fujiwara clan acted as regents and when the emperor came of age, they acted as the chief advisor of the emperor as well as continued to run the government as they wished. This was called the "Regency Government".

The power of the Fujiwara clan reached its peak during the reign of Fujiwara-no-Michinaga in the first half of the 11th century. He had four daughters as wives of the Emperor's and held the actual power of politics for a long time.

2. Background

The phase of classical Japan started with Asuka period and ended with Heian period.

The duration of Asuka period was 538-710 CE. The major incidents which happened in this period-

- Buddhism flourished
- Chinese Influence
- Naming to “Nippon”
- Establishment of Japan's first constitution by Emperor Shotoku Taishi
- Ritsuryo System
- Taika reforms and Taiho code
- Emergence of Fujiwara clan
- Horyu-ji temple

After Asuka period, the Nara period came and it existed from 710 to 794 CE. The key features of this period was-

- Nara capital
- Disasters
- Promotion of Buddhism
- Toda-ji temple
- Factional fights
- Chinese Tang dynasty influence
- Silk route

The last period of classical Japan started the movement of Capital from Nara to Nagaoka-kyo and then Heian-kyo. This period was named “Heian period” which means peace. This is also called the Golden Age of Japan as this period saw a flourishing on economic, social and cultural field.

3. Analysis

3.1 When Japan Emperors had actual power

At the beginning of the Heian period, Japan was more unified than it had ever been. Emperors had actual power. The capital had decent control over the provinces. But things would begin to fall apart.

The early Heian Emperors wanted to be the Chinese ideal of an absolute ruler and they came as close to it as they had ever got. They were Kanmu, Heizei, Saga, Junna and Ninmyo. This was a period from 781 to 850. Even before the Heian, Japanese Emperors tried to model their government after that of the Sui and Tang dynasties of China. But they began to realize that what worked in China didn't necessarily work in Japan. China had rulers with absolute power. In Japan, the top clans in court were too strong for the Imperial family to control, it was a constant tug of war. China appointed government officials using a civil service exam. One got his job based on how he did, based on merit. In Japan, the clans thought that was silly. They thought that "Positions are best awarded based on clan connections and marital ties".

When Emperor Kanmu ascended the throne in 781, he was part of a new line of emperors. Almost literally, it was a new bloodline. More than a century before, after Emperor Tenji died, Emperor Tenmu seized the throne from Tenji's son. Afterwards, Tenmu's descendants occupied the throne for most of the Nara period. His descendants were called the Tenmu line. But near the end of the Nara period, they were running low on Tenmu descendants and head to enthrone Emperor Konin. He was a grandson of old Emperor Tenji, so the throne switched back to the Tenji line. Konin's son was Emperor Kanmu, the first emperor of the Heian era, often called the most powerful Japanese emperor in terms of his authority.

When Kanmu became emperor in 781, the court happened to be devoid of any strong Fujiwara clansmen. The Fujiwara was at the time the biggest challenged to imperial authority. With their long shadow absent from the court, Kanmu acted immediately. In 784, he took his capital and went home. Literally, he moved the capital out of Nara to Nagaoka-kyo, his maternal home. He probably wanted to wrench the court away from the grip of Buddhist power in Nara and away from the entrenched Nara politicians who had strong ties with the Tenmu line. It was an opportunity to resume the Tenji line with a blank state. But soon shenanigans went down in Nagaoka-kyo. Someone killed Kanmu's chief advisor and the blame fell on his brother, who escaped exile via suicide by starvation. More deaths and diseases came. So, Kanmu moved the capital again in 794 to Heian-kyo, kicking off the Heian Period with a balling palace based on Chinese capitals. 794 was the middle of China's Tang Dynasty and around the time Charlemagne became the first Holy Roman Emperor.

The biggest problem early Heian emperors faced was money. They were running out of it. Kanmu started wars against barbarians to the north. This along with creating new capitals was a huge drain on government coffers, but the main culprits were more insidious.

The new offices quickly made large chunks of the government obsolete. By the late 800s, half of the old government positions were slashed, the number of government officials plummeted. This saved money and made things more efficient, but it also further pushed people away from the capital into the provincial governments.

Another money-saving plan they had was the purge of Imperial Family members. In this case, the descendants of an emperor were considered princes or princesses. This applied as far down as the 5th or even the 6th generation descendant. And if anyone were a member of Lucky Gamete Club, he was given riches, land and respect. Considering the fact that the emperors had a hard time keeping it in their pants, Saga had 49 kids, it was a huge drain on resources. Emperor Kanmu started practice of kicking people out of his house, his Imperial House. He declared that anyone born from an emperor after the 4th generations was not royalty and demoted more than a hundred members of the Imperial House. Emperor Saga even demoted a bunch of his own first-generation descendants, aka his kids. He probably didn't know, he had 49 of them. Demotion happened this way.

It has to be noticed that members of the Imperial House did not have a surname. Members who were ousted were given a clan name. Minamoto was the most prestigious name. Children of emperors usually got this name. The second generation and below were given less prestigious names like Taira.

The court also reduced the money that went to Imperial Family members, causing unimportant members to be living in near-poverty. Many of these poor and demoted princes fled to the provinces seeking opportunity, further strengthening the provincial noble class.

Still running low on funds, the court began paying its officials in land. Turned out this weakened the central government even more. Certain government offices received land to use as a source of revenue. And because they had a source of income separate from the court, it weakened the court's control over them. This growth of private lands for public offices happened at the same time that the number of shoen was increasing in the provinces. Even worse, the absence of a powerful Fujiwara clan pushing back against imperial power allowed emperor to amass land for themselves and their family. These were private lands for the emperor, not public. It left even less land for the state to draw revenue from.

3.2 End of Emperor rule in Japan

The Japanese court in Heian period went through three phases, where the power passed from the emperors to the Fujiwara, then to the retired emperors. This section will discuss the middle period of Heian era.

Fujiwara clan was founded long before the Heian by Nakatomi no Kamatari, who helped overthrow the Soga clan because they had too much power over the Japanese court. But after years later his own Fujiwara clan would take over the courts. The clan split into 4 main houses. By the Heian period, the Northern house, the Hokke, became the strongest and dominated the court. Their secret superpower was “Ladies”.

It became customary for emperors to marry Fujiwara ladies. If they were into non-Fujiwara ladies, they could have multiple consorts. They just had to make sure that the main consort was a woman of imperial blood or a Fujiwara. That wasn't just a custom, that was the law.

FUJIWARA ACT

**1. Main consort =
Imperial Family,
Fujiwara**

**2. Only Fujiwara men
can marry daughters
of emperors**

In 857, Fujiwara no Yoshifusa became chancellor, the highest office in government. And in 858, Yoshifusa's 9-year-old grandson took the throne as Emperor Seiwa. Because the emperor was so young, Yoshifusa basically took control and unofficially ruled in his stead. And then in 866, one of the gates of the imperial palace burned down. Through an investigation pointed to the old Otomo and Ki clans and they suffered a serious exile of their ranks. The Otomo and Ki were ancient clans, they were the old guard, the major opposition to the Fujiwara. And they had just been removed from the board. Some say it was the Fujiwara who orchestrated the whole fire, some say they just took advantage of an opportunity.

The same year, Yoshifusa officially became sessho, or regent. He ruled on behalf of Emperor Seiwa. It was the first time someone outside the royal family became regent. Emperor Seiwa was famous for holding the totally unimpressive honour of being the first child-emperor of Japan. He also held the equally unimpressive honour of being the first male emperor to have a regent rule for him. The trend started with Seiwa. After him came a whole bunch of child emperors.

Yoshifusa's son Fujiwara no Motosune became regent in 884, a new adult emperor ascended. A regent was only supposed to rule on behalf of a child emperor, he would have had to step down. He solved the problem by creating a new title: Kanpaku.

Kanpaku	Sessho
Regent for adult emperor	Regent for child emperor

The others in the court did challenge Mototsune. They'd have been rude not to. But he won, and the fact that he won made it a huge deal. It made the kanpaku position permanent, and always held by the Northern Fujiwara House. This is a great example of the trend the Heian where people valued clan loyalty over loyalty of the state. The Northern Fujiwara House, became known as the Sekkanke, or the Regent house. Fujiwara power became entrenched for the next 200 years.

They took advantage of how Heian marriages worked. In Heian Japan, the emperor's eldest son was not automatically the heir. It was the emperor's choice. Usually the heir came down to the prince with the most support in court, and since the Fujiwara the court, the heir was usually a Fujiwara. Also within Heian aristocracy, children were raised in the household of the maternal grandfather. That is, they were raised by the mother's side. So one had a situation where emperors married Fujiwara women and their potential heirs were then raised by the Fujiwara clan. A clan that raises future emperors is a clan that succeeds.

There were challenges to the state of things from time to time, like the sad story of Sugawara no Michizane. Michizane was a rising star in the court, rising all the way from an insignificant clan to a senior position in court. He had the backing of emperor, who groomed him to be the Immovable Object to the Fujiwara Unstoppable Force, Though Michizane himself thought someone as lowborn as him had no business being in a position so high. He was also really a good poet. Fearing a strong enemy, the Fujiwara accused Michizane of conspiracy. He was devoted, exiled and the Immovable Object moved six feet under.

In the years following his death, the Fujiwara household stuck by misfortune and by lightning. A disastrous lightning storm killed and injured some people. Similar to what happened with Emperor Sutoku, people blamed Michizane's spirit for the storm. Fearing the spirit, the court un-exiled Michizane and restored his rank. After that, a cult developed around Michizane. People began to worship him as a kami, a god. First as a kami of thunder and lightning, then as a kami of learning and education. They called him Tenjin and people still pray to Tenjin today.

“When I reflect, this world is indeed mine.” – Michinaga

3.3 Life of early Japanese peasants

Getting married was different in Heian period. The husband and wife didn't immediately move out and live together.

The Heian era is known for art and culture and nobles living posh lives. These things made a tiny spark of the population. Almost the entire aristocracy lived in the capital of Heian-kyo. Japan at that time had the population of 6 to 7 million people. The capital had 100 to 150 thousand people. And the aristocracy made up only 1 to 2 percent of the capital's population. Even, the people who held any actual influence in the government numbered only 100 to 125 men.

Outside the capital, Japan was still an agrarian culture and based on rice farming. They didn't have villages even. Peasants lived in loose settlements and households were mostly independent. It was common for a house to be more than 100 metres away from the next house. Because of their independence, households were pretty big, about 8 to 10 people.

Life in Heian Period; Source: Sutori.com

Marriage arrangements among the peasants happened like this. It was similar to aristocratic marriages. The wife got the short end of the stick with regards to responsibility. The husband basically visited to make sperm deposits, then went on his merry way. Newlyweds didn't move into a new home. They stayed separate, living in their own parents' household. The husband would visit his wife once in a while at night. Then he just go back home. Children were raised in the wife's household. This phase of living separately wasn't permanent most of the time. Although in some communities, it would last for the entire marriage.

This marriage situation gave them some interesting family dynamics. On the up side, kids were raised in a home where there were always people to take care them. The wife had more freedom than if she had lived in the home of her husband's or the in-law's. The down side the husband had less freedom because he still lives under his parent's. This also gave a lot of rights to older generation over the lives of the younger generation. A new couple didn't just move out and escaped their parents' control because of wet rice farming.

In the Heian period, people used transplanting method for rice farming. Transplanting is different from direct seeding. This process required more people than one family had, so families had to hire help. And this is why couples couldn't survive if they had moved out immediately after marriage.

As if farming life wasn't tough enough, the Japanese court did something that made life even tougher. But the hardy peasants turned a bad thing into something that made them even more successful. One of the responsibilities of the state was to ensure the public could freely use uncultivated land. The rich could not reserve free land for their own use. Commoners used free lands for all purposes like grazing animals, collecting wood etc. But over time, the state started to give more and more uncultivated land to temples, shrines and powerful clans. These land grants shrunk the amount of land available for grazing. So, the peasant fed their horses another food called rice stalks. This actually introduced a new source of income for farmers, selling hay to animal owners. As the animals had to keep house in this time, the availability of poo increased crop fields. In theory, the labour cost of transplanting and the monetary cost of ploughs should have encouraged people to form closer and larger communities. But it didn't see. Peasants household remained independent in Heian.

3.4 Life of Early Japanese Women

The life of the upper class women of Heian period was extreme boredom, interrupted by casual cheating.

The aristocratic and upper class women of Heian period lead a life of contradictions.

Contradictions

1. Much Freedom, But stuck in house

2. Inferior to Men, and More Valuable

1. Much freedom, but stuck in house

Upper class women had lives of luxury and high status. But at the same time they had almost no freedom to move about. Women mostly stayed at home. A woman was expected to be hidden from outside men, the only men she saw were her father and husband. Women had private quarters and stayed concealed behind screens. To attend an occasion or visit a temple, women could come outside only. Even, they did social interactions without using mouth. Actual talking through the mouth was done with her father, husband, female servants and female visitors. Court ladies wrote letters and poems to communicate outside their home. Sometimes, they met the male in vast occasion but that also behind the screen or in another room. They spoke with the visitors through notes or female servants. They were the proper ladies, didn't do households, had proper servants to take care of her children. Just they had to stick at home. One woman wrote a diary of this era was found later. There was written-

“17th day of the month.

There is a slow drizzle.

My direction today is unlucky and so I can expect no visitors.

The world seems a dearie, cheerless place.”

Women tried different ways to have fun like calligraphy, music, and sewing. But most famously, they wrote stuff. From their writings many things of the Heian period found out. So, women mainly crushed men in literature. Women made the Japanese written language popular in Japan. Contrast to most cultures, famous Heian authors were almost all women. The main reasons behind this are thought to be-

- Men wrote more seriously and women wrote with creativity.
- Men were in government and they wrote in Chinese as it was official language. But women were not in government. So, they learnt new Japanese language of Hiragana instead of Chinese. They spread today's Japanese written form (Hiragana and Katakana) through diaries, poems, fictions and non- fictitious.

2. Inferior to Men, and More Valuable

Chinese Confucian teachings and Chinese Buddhist teachings at that time weren't playing around, they hammered home the idea that women were inferior. Buddhist teachings claimed that a women had to reincarnate into a men before ascending higher in the path to enlightenment. Women were banned from government. At the same time,

- Women were often considered more valuable than men because of marriage politics. The Fujiwara clan married their daughters into imperial family and secured 200 years of control over the government.
- Inheritance of property usually went to women over men, giving them significant economic freedom.
- Violence against women was prohibited.
- A wife didn't actually join her husband's clan. She kept her own clan name and after death was buried among her own members.

The Heian period had a pretty imaginative fashion sense. White skin was considered attractive. So, women used rich powder to paint their faces and necks pure white. But, white teeth was not considered attractive and teeth looked like of yellow against that of white skin. So, women blackened their teeth. They plucked their eyebrows, replacing them with painted eye blotches. Long straight hair was beautiful. A woman took care in coordinating the colours of her outfits and putting together right ensemble to reflect her personality.

Women in the Heian court; Source: owlcation

Marriage was highly regarded in Heian period between man and women relations. But most commonly, they did extramarital relations. It was a time of sexual freedom. That time, virginity of a girl considered a curse, a long possessed by an evil spirit.

3.5 The Seduction Game

The famous novel written during the Heian period named “The Tale of Genji”. The main character of this novel was Genji who sees a woman and becomes thirsty as hell. Without warning, he picks her up and rushes her to a private room. In the room, he sets her down and she is frightened. Genji requests that she sleeps with him but she flat out and says no. Genji doesn’t quit and tries different ways to coerce her verbally. She denies him again and again. But after a while, she relents and they sleep together. That’s all. But what Genji did was kidnapping, sexual harassment, sexual assault and may be even rape. Some scholars claim that what he did was wrong even by Heian standards. But other scholars disagreed saying that Genji’s behaviour was okay by Heian standards. Now, this later group is discussed about.

Tale of Genji; Source: Britannica

The “Tale of Genji” was written by Murasaki Shikibu, a female writer. His main character Genji is portrayed as the good guy throughout the story. He is the hero. She would make him good in everything else, but a monster to women. Heian love was different. The upper class people of Heian like the weakness of women. They usually tied love to the emotion of pity. They often fell in love because Heian women had some negative qualities that made them seem pathetic. A typical seduction technique was to show that they were vulnerable, weak, powerless so that the other person would feel pity or compassion for her. Even, it was also true for men. A man would off show his weakness by shedding tears when he dropped his fan. This idea

wasn't new in Japan. The Chinese at the time had similar ideas. Weakness in women aroused desire.

So, in the "Tale of Genji" Genji was playing the 'Heian Seduction game'. There were three bases;

- Aggression
- Persuasion
- Success

And women had two reactions;

- Saying "No"
- Becoming Passive

3.6 Romance in Early Japan

The whole process starts with the matchmaker. First of all, the matchmaker would let a man or his family know of a lady who would be a good candidate. Then both families had to look at all kinds of factors to determine if the two were a good match. What was not a factor was the opinion of the couple. It was very much an arranged marriage for political, economic or social gain. The woman's family wanted a husband who had good connections that would allow him to rise the ranks in court, preferably a husband who already had a high rank. The man's family wanted a wife from a family that had enough wealth and resources to support him in his government career. Daughters of powerful clans so had a bunch of men chasing after them. A common trope in Heian literature was the wife battle where multiple men would compete for a woman's hand in marriage. "The Tale of the Bamboo" is the best example of this.

After all the discussion and negotiation, if each family swipes right, the matchmaker would set things up. Then, the dating ritual would commence. The whole process consisted of an initiation and three visits.

First of all, the groom wrote a romantic poem to the bride with 31 syllables, which is called "Tanka". Then, the bride wrote a response poem. This poem was important. If the poem of the bride liked by the groom, they made plans to secretly meet at her place at night and they slept together. This was the first visit. He left early morning as it was customary. Then, the "Next-morning letter" sent the groom to the bride. It contained the last night was very well. After that,

the bride's family sent gift and drinks with the responded letter. The next night, again the groom visited the bride house quietly and left like the first night. On the third visit, the bride's family made rice cakes called “Miyako mochi” and kept that in her room. In Heian Japan, there was not any legal paper to recognise the marriage rather if their family and friends recognised them as married, a couple was married. The couple goes through two small rituals.

1. The rice cakes were to honour the Shinto gods Izanagi and Izanami. Eating the cakes united the couple religiously.
2. Eating with the wife's family along with friends. But the groom's parents didn't present there.

In the case of secondary marriage, all of these happened as like as. But it took long time to completed the marriage.

3.7 Marriage in Early Japan

Marriages in Heian period were different what we are used to. Heian Japan was a polygamous society. To be more specific, they practiced polygyny which means each husband could have multiple wives. Like most polygamous society, the majority if Heian nobles only choose to have one wife and three wives were rare.

A man's first marriage was not for love, but for clan and career. People married at a young age, probably as young as 11. Not all wives got the sane honour. A man's first wife was his main one and other wives had to respect her position. The first wife was like a cougar. She was usually older than the husband. According to Confucian tradition, she was expected to be faithful and obedient and provide her husband a son.

For the secondary wife or concubine, the marriage was not so traditional as first one. It was comparatively casual. Secondary wives were usually much younger than the husband. The position of the secondary wife was also shaky.

Expectations

Husband	Main wife	Secondary wife
1. Large Family	1. Small Family	1. Small Family
2. Strategic Marriage	2. Respect	2. Control over the husband
3. Continue Lineage	3. Children's Status	

With the pace of time, the practice of living separate after marriage decreased. A couple could live their own home as soon as they married and that home was provided by the wife's family. But over the time, this responsibility also shifted to the husband's family. Though the husband was not obliged to take care of his wife and children, the wife had to live in the husband's house until their death even after divorce. The wife specifically her family needed to provide house, money, clothing to the husband always.

Divorce in the Heian period was basically ghosting. It was really easy to do, by both men and women. The legal code had the concept of divorce but trying to pinpoint the exact date of a divorce. There was no legal paper or sign. When husband didn't meet wife for a long time, it considered as divorce. But most of the time, the husband came back after a decade. So, it was not sure that was it a divorce or a break?

Women was safe from bodily harm. It was against the law for a husband to beat his wife and certainly against the law to kill her except in one case. It's interesting because the open secret in Heian society was that everyone cheated. In theory, wives were expected to be faithful but

they were not and everyone knew it. However, if a husband caught his wife in act with another man, he could actually kill her.

3.8 Buddhism and Shintoism in Early Japan

The history of Heian period will remain incomplete without the discussion of religion. Two Buddhist sects became all the range in Heian Japan.

- Tendai
- Shingon

When Emperor Kanmu moved the capital from Nara to Heian-kyo for escaping from the powerful Buddhist temples, it opened the door for new schools. Saicho and Kukai were two monks who studied Buddhism in China. After returned back to Japan, they had a collusion and they built two different school of Buddhism. Saicho founded the Tendai school and Kukai founded the Shingon school. Both school rejected the old sacred doctrine. Saicho created the famous Tendai Monastery Enryakuji on Mount Hiei overlooking the capital of Heian-kyo. Enryakuji was not only a Buddhist temple that taught Buddhism it also became a political and economic powerhouse. Tendai followers taught that the way to understand Buddha's teachings was through studying sacred texts like "Lotus Sutra". On the contrary, the Shingon followers thought that the enlightenment was by experiencing the truth of the universe via rituals like Mantras (Chants), Mudras (Hand signs) and Mandalas (Ass drawings).

Tendai was the more powerful of the two. It enjoyed backing of the Fujiwara House and the Imperial Family. Bit Shingon was popular to other Heian elites.

In Heian era, religious treatment of women changed. When Buddhism spread to China, they incorporated Taoist and Confucian thought which were not so egalitarian. They introduced the idea of blood pollution. Women's menstrual and birthing blood were impure and so they prevented salvation. Women had to reincarnate into men before they could attain enlightenment. Women also polluted temples ground with their cooties. This Cootie Buddhism spread to Japan. Before, women were allowed to be trained in temples as nun. But in the Heian period, most temple stopped that. Though after the Heian period, this did not exist.

Powerful Buddhist temples trained warrior monks called “Sohei”. These were much like the monastic orders of Catholic warrior monks in Europe. Enryakuji on Mount Hiei was a huge training ground for warrior monks.

Though Buddhism practiced more in Heian period, the majority of the country’s common folk practiced Shintoism.

3.9 Fujiwara Clan

Fujiwara clan found themselves at the top of the government and they removed their enemies so that the government did not collapse. The Fujiwara Family married their daughters into the Imperial Family which was allowing them to control over the Heian court for 200 years, from around 850 to 1068. The clan was founded by Nakatomi no Kamatari after he helped rid the court of the tyrannical Soga clan in 645.

Symbol of Fujiwara Clan; Source: Redbubble

It became accepted that the Fujiwara would hold the title of regent. If the emperor was a child, the Fujiwara regent will be Sessho and if the emperor was adult, the Fujiwara regent would be Kenpaku. It became that the emperor was child and the regent ruled instead of the emperor. Over time, the Fujiwara clan members grabbed all of the top government positions. At the height of their power, a man named Fujiwara no Michinaga sat at the head of the clan. He was the strongest of them all and the apex politician in court. He actually only held the regent position for one year. Then slid it to his son. For the two decades afterwards Michinaga controlled over the court as the court document inspector, a lower-ranked position. Just goes to show that Fujiwara power did not come from the regent position, it came from the family name and the number of Fujiwara allies and members they had in government.

Michinaga noticed that the warrior class rising outside the capital, the minor provinces. So, they made friendship with a little clan named Minamoto. But they had well position in the military of the court. Among them, two main generals were Minamoto no Yorimitsu and Minamoto no Yorinobu. Michinaga also used public fund for his interest that's why the this era was called the golden age of Fujiwara clan. He died at the age of 62.

There was also conflict within the Fujiwara clan that was disputed by the internal offices. So the Fujiwara had a kind of parallel government structure running alongside the official government. In the Heian period, the government started to provide tax-free land or "Shoen" to temples and government officials as payment or rewards. The Fujiwara accumulated a largest number of Shoen. In this period, the government wasn't in good position. They were gradually losing tax revenue and influence.

3.10 Collapsing of Fujiwara clan

It all started when Emperor Go-Sanjo took the throne in 1068. Before ascending the throne he had been the crown prince for 23 years. Because of being an adult of 33 years and first emperor in 170 years not to have a Fujiwara mother, he had not any loyalty for Fujiwara clan. Rather, he was an allies of Minamoto clan. He launched his political war with an attack against Shoen. He ordered an inspection of shoen documents. As there was no written documents were found, Go-Sanjo returned all shoen. In 1072, Emperor Go-Sanjo

stepped down to retire to a monastery giving the throne to his son Emperor Shirakawa. He did this for excluding the influence of Fujiwara. He died after some days.

Then, Emperor Shirakawa ruled the throne and he also retired once time. But he returned after few days. Liked other emperors, he created his own emperor's office called "In-no-cho". He began hundred years of "Insei" which means cloistered rule. Here the government was ruled by retired emperors. So, the emperor was a figurehead as the retired emperor was the main ruler. But they were also losing the control over the provinces. In this case, they provided the land among the imperial family members without tax as like before. Just the exception was that the shoen system was controlled by the Fujiwara Clan and this time it was the Imperial Family.

3.11 Hogen & Heiji Rebellion

Hogen rebellion of 1156 pitted father against son, uncle against nephew and brother against brother. It started with the famous rivalry between two warrior class: the Taira and the Minamoto. It was a sign that change was coming in Japan. Hogen was just the name of era when it happened. It ended the dominance of the Fujiwara family over the monarchy and signalled the beginning of a protected period of feudal welfare.

The battle started as a disagreement between the ruling emperor Go-Shirakawa and the emperor who was retired named Sutoku about who would dominate the imperial court. Sutoku summoned a group of Minamoto and Taira troops under the command of Minamoto Tameyoshi, the head of the Fujiwara clan and had held the role of chief counsellor or Kampaku since 857, sided with Go-Shirakawa. The opposite side was subsequently helped by a new squad of warriors led by Taira Kiyomori. The forces of Kiyomori won; Tameyoshi was put to death and Sutoku was banished. But as it became clear that the leadership of Fujiwara was unsuccessful, the Taira family effectively took over the ruled of the government.

Minamoto Yoshitomo, the commander of the Minamoto soldiers that had joined forces with Taira Kiyomori in 1156, made an attempt at a coup defeat against the Taira leadership 3 years later. Following the "Heiji Disturbance" (Heiji no run), Kiyomori won and the Taira strengthened their control over the nation.

The rebellion of Hogen and Heiji Eras; Source: Metropolitan Museum of Art

3.12 The First Samurai

Taira-no-Masakado was born into the strongest branch of Taira clan. Historian Karl Friday calls him the first samurai. It was not sure but Masakado was a very early Samurai leader. He was descended from Emperor Kanmu.

Masakado took control of a region in Central Japan called Kanto in 939. He then used the legend surrounding his ancestry as the new Emperor(Shinno) to establish his own court and name governor's for Japan's eight northern provinces. Masakado killed several of his relatives, including three uncles, in the fight for power. An incident which is named as the "Tengy no ran" (War in the Tengy era), he was finally subdued by two local rivals. The uprising signalled the weakening central government's control over rural areas and heralded the rise of formidable warlord families in the provinces, among which the Taira clan later rose to become one of the most potent.

3.13 Genpei War

The Kamakura Shogunate which was known as military dictatorship that ruled Japan from 1192 to 1333, was founded by the Minamoto clan after the Genpei War (1180-85), the last conflict in Japan between the Taira and Minamoto clan.

From 1160 to 1185, the Taira clan held sway over the imperial administration. The great Minamoto leader Yoshitomo's son, Minamoto Yoritomo, was spared after his father was defeated in 1160 because of his youth. He seized the opportunity presented by the developing discontent with the Taira leadership in 1180 to plan a fresh uprising on behalf of not only Taira but also Minamoto families. He quickly took over Japan's strategically important east coast and by 1182, he was prepared to invade the Kyoto capital. The young monarch Antoku was taken with the Taira leaders as they fled. The Taira were finally vanquished in the naval battle of Dannoura (1185) in the inland sea in Western Japan. The famous sword that was one of the Imperial Treasures of Japan and was allegedly brought from heaven by the first Japanese monarch was lost when the emperor Antoku drowned during the battle. Through natives like the Genpei seisui-ki, the conflict rose to legendary status.

Genpei war; Source: Anticstore

3.14 Culture in Heian Period

This period is also a time of cultural blossoming. The Japanese court exploded into words and paint. China was a source of high culture and if anyone wanted to be a government official, he had better learn to read Chinese and understand Chinese culture, Confucianism and Buddhism. Confucian and Buddhist texts repeated over and over again not only how to govern justly but

also how to be a moral person, according to the Chinese. A bunch of classics came out of the Heian era, such as “The Tale of Genji” and “The Pillow Book”. The Japanese written scripts of Hiragana and Katakana were also created in this era. Buddhist temples commissioned a bunch of Buddha paintings and sculptures. But art started expanding into the non-Buddha realm as well artists began to realize that they were able to paint regular-sized ears. This cultural flowering also started to seep outside the Heian court and into the life of commoners who were known to read or at least listen to court literature. There were travelling bards who spread stories and music among the common folk.

4. Summary

The Heian period was started when the Japanese capital was moved to Heian-kyo which is modern day Kyoto. It was a time of massive political change and culture. In this period, the Japanese emperor lost his power and became a figurehead. The emperor would not have any real authority again until the modern age. The power of the government passed from the emperor to the Fujiwara clan for 200 years and then to the retired emperor for another hundred years. Then, Japan had the military takeover.

5. Conclusion

After Genpei war, Minamoto Yoritomo established military government in the city of Kamakura. So, through the arising of Samurai class, the Heian period was completed. Besides, Classical Japanese era which started on Asuka period, expanded on Nara period and flourished on Heian period came to an end. Through the Kamakura period, the next 400 years of Feudal Japanese era came on light. In the establishment of today’s Japan, Heian period took an important role. Specially, the diversity of political power, development of major cultural elements like “Tale of Genji” and “The Pillow Book”, spread of Buddhism and Shintoism according to the Japanese own principles rather imitating the Chinese perspective, the invasion of First Samurai class etc. were the key features of the “Golden Age of Japan”. Cultivating these elements in future, Japan flourishing their historical timeline and became one of the developed countries of the world.

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